

The role of policies for a sustainable EOSC

Summary of the webinar on 27th October 2020

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Related documents:

This document will be published as part of D3.2 ‘Final report on the communities and usage of services’ in Summer 2022 by the EOSC-Pillar project.

1 Introduction

Policies are cornerstones on the road to Open Science (OS) and FAIR data and prominent aspects of the ‘readiness’ or sustainability of countries and initiatives concerning the implementation of EOSC. Whether there are national and institutional policies in place, what they address and what their consequences are and more generally, the status and developments of the OS policy framework is considered essential to making progress in the OS movement and establishing OS practices in the research community.

The webinar organised by EOSC-Pillar on 27th October 2020 aimed at outlining existing research on OS policies as well as getting insights by experts working in the field. This document contains the summary of the webinar. In the beginning of the webinar, Lisa Hönegger (EOSC-Pillar) presented the findings on policies of the ‘National Initiatives’ survey conducted by EOSC-Pillar (Section 2). Then, Vanessa Proudman (SPARC Europe, FAIRsFAIR) and Joy Davidson (DCC, FAIRsFAIR) summarized the key findings of their long lasting research on policies across Europe (Section 3). Section 2 and 3 hold an overview of the two presentations. In some instances, we also included references to the documents that the speaker cited in their presentations in order to give interested readers the opportunity to dive deeper into the material. In the second part of the webinar, expert panelists provided insights into policies from different angles and enriched the discussion with their experiences in different fields (e.g. universities, funding organisations, OS initiatives). Section 4 contains the key arguments of this discussion.

The focus of the webinar was on the following questions:

1. What are the effects of policies and why are policies important?
2. What are the interdependencies of national and institutional policies?
3. What are the consequences for researchers for (not) complying with policies? What are incentives for researchers to comply with policies?
4. What are the lessons learned from the open access movement and the adoption of open access policies?

More information on the webinar, the agenda and the recording are available on the EOSC-Pillar website: <https://eosc-pillar.eu/events/webinar-role-policies-sustainable-eosc>.

2 The status quo of policies for Open Science and FAIR data

Input presentation I by **Lisa Hönegger (EOSC-Pillar)**

EOSC-Pillar, as one of the regional EOSC support projects, aims at coordinating national and regional initiatives on open data and services in five countries: Austria, Belgium, France, Germany and Italy. The project conducted a survey comprising also the current status on the existence and content of policies that aim at supporting OS and FAIR data (Bodlos et al., 2020a, 2020b). During her presentation, Lisa Hönegger (2020) gave an overview of the survey results with a focus on universities and funding bodies.

EOSC-Pillar has asked representatives of **funding bodies** whether their ‘organisation impose(s) rules for funding on grant recipients’ (Bodlos et al., 2020c, 25) regarding several aspects of OS and FAIR data. According to the gathered data, ‘data management plans’ (40%) and ‘open access publications’ (36%) are most common among binding regulations by funding bodies for (some of) their grants. Funding bodies also often have regulations in place for ‘open research data’ (32%), the ‘compliance of data to the FAIR principles’ (32%), the ‘publication of data in a repository’ (28%) and the ‘long-term availability of research data’ (28%). However, only two of 25 funding bodies who responded indicated to condition grants on the ‘publication of data in a certified repository’ (Bodlos et al., 2020a, 106–107).

Of course, forcing grant receivers to comply with certain regulations is not the only way to foster OS practices. As the ‘National Initiatives’ survey shows, up to 40% of the funding bodies also ‘encourage’ applicants to pursue OS and FAIR data standards (Bodlos et al., 2020a, 107).

EOSC-Pillar has also surveyed representatives of **universities** as universities also can promote OS among researchers. As the results show, across countries, more than half of the universities have on average policies and formal regulations on ‘open access publication’ in place. However, EOSC-Pillar noted large differences between the five countries: Whereas all Belgian universities reported to have regulations for open access publications, these phenomenon is less prevalent in the other Pillar-countries (Bodlos et al., 2020a, 107, 110).

Compared to open access publications, universities less frequently launch regulations in other fields of OS and FAIR data. On average, a little more than one quarter regulate the ‘publication of data in a repository’ and ‘research data management (RDM)’ and even less enforce the ‘long-term availability of research data’, the ‘publication of data

in a certified repository’ and the ‘compliance of data to the FAIR principles’ and ‘open research data’ (Bodlos et al., 2020a, 107–109).

Similar to the funding bodies, universities do not only rely on binding regulations, but also nudge affiliated researchers to take up OS practices: Roughly one third indicated the presence of ‘informal regulations’. Despite all these formal and informal regulations of OS, many universities still refrain from regulations in this regard (Bodlos et al., 2020a, 109).

3 ‘Policies are an important instrument to accelerate embedding FAIR into the research life cycle’

Input presentation II by **Vanessa Proudman (SPARC Europe, FAIRsFAIR)** and **Joy Davidson (DCC, FAIRsFAIR)**

As a second input presentation, Vanessa Proudman and Joy Davidson (2020) offered glimpses into their work on OS policies across Europe:

One aim of FAIRsFAIR is promoting the FAIR principles and one way to do so is via policies (Sveinsdottir, Proudman, & Davidson, 2020). Last year, SPARC Europe, in collaboration with Science Europe, EFC and ALLEA, analysed policies of **funding bodies**, especially with regard to OS (Fosci, Richens, & Johnson, 2019). Similar to the results of the ‘National Initiatives’ Survey, they found that open access policies are more common among funding bodies than other policies. In more detail, Fosci et al. (2019) reported:

- Open access: Of the 61 funding organisations in the analysis, 37 already have adopted an Open Access (OA) policy, the vast majority of these even have obligatory regulations. 24 funding bodies have renounced an OA policy so far. However, the authors found that half of these 24 funding organisations are working towards such an OA policy (Fosci et al., 2019, 6).
- Open Science: Of all 61 funding organisations in the analysis, 19 have an OS policy in place. Of these 19 organisations, 12 have adopted a ‘Research Data policy’ specifically for data. These frequencies also imply that 42 funding organisations do not have adopted such policies, but a substantial share (13 organisations) is pursuing this goal (Fosci et al., 2019, 6).
- Besides, funding bodies audit compliance with open access policies more frequently than other policies (Fosci et al., 2019, 7).

However, Vanessa Proudman concludes that there is progress in the development of policies, hence, the landscape may very well change in the future.

SPARC Europe has also conducted research for FAIRsFAIR on **national policies** (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020), some key results are: The FAIR principles are part of several national policies, but not of all (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 16). Likewise, a definition of ‘research data’ is not part of all policies. However, the speaker highlights the ‘National Plan for Open Science’ in France as an example of a national policy comprising a clear definition (Ministère de l’enseignement supérieur, de la recherche et de l’innovation, 2018, see also Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 11). Concerning ‘mandates’ or ‘requirements’ rather than ‘recommendations’ to sharing data, SPARC Europe/FAIRsFAIR observed that several national policies ‘suggest’ or ‘recommend’ sharing data, but binding regulations are the exception rather than the rule (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 12). Likewise, Data management plans (DMPs) are more frequently ‘recommended’ than ‘required’ (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 17).

Following the principle that data should be ‘as open as possible but as closed as necessary’, e.g. ‘where data relates to national security, or where there are issues relating to confidentiality, privacy, intellectual property rights, and trade secrets’ (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 13), SPARC Europe found that only a minority of the national policies contained clear specifications on the justifications for not publishing research data. Noteworthy examples are the UK, Slovenia and Norway (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 13–14).

An important aspect of OS are incentives for sharing data, e.g. to enhance the prestige of publishing data and to encourage citing data. Only a minority of national policies (e.g. Switzerland, Ireland, Norway and the UK) contain ‘expectations on data citations’ (Sveinsdottir et al., 2020, 17–18).

Of course, adopting policies is only the first step. SPARC Europe therefore has also investigated whether funding organisations keep an eye on whether criteria established in their policies are respected. As the survey among 35 funding organisation shows, compliance with open access policies is watched more frequently than compliance with other aspects of OS. Funding organisations most frequently indicated that a ‘lack of adequate monitoring infrastructure or tools’ was responsible for the absence of systematic monitoring (Fosci et al., 2019, 22–24).

FAIRsFAIR has formulated several recommendations on policies (Davidson et al., 2020). Key recommendations are to formulate ‘a common set of FAIR policy elements’ (Davidson et al., 2020, 8) that shall then be part of policies. Other recommendations refer to enhancing the accessibility and version control of policies as well as to making policies comparable via machine-readability. Besides, comparing policies also requires taking implicit descriptions of FAIR components into account (Davidson et al., 2020). In terms of measurement, there is no widely acknowledged consensus on how to measure FAIRness especially with respect to discipline specific differences. Hence, one challenge

is finding set of ‘minimal viable metrics’ for FAIR data (Proudman & Davidson, 2020)¹. Recommendations concerning Data Management Plans are regulations on updates of this document (Davidson et al., 2020, 22). Also the speaker suggests to ‘(r)eward good practice, but where necessary, **penalties** for non-compliance should be considered’ (Proudman & Davidson, 2020, 23).

4 Summary of the expert discussion

This section contains an overview of the most salient arguments made in the discussion. This summary does neither implicate a consensus among all panellists nor that all participants stated their view on all topics.

Panelists:

Joy Davidson (Digital Curation Center)
Matthias Fingerhuth (FDM NRW)
Sverker Holmgren (The Guild)
Jan Hrušák (EOOSC Landscape Working Group)
Vanessa Proudman (SPARC Europe)
Marie Timmermann (Science Europe)

Moderator:

Rob Carillo (EOOSC-Pillar)
Federica Tanlongo (EOOSC-Pillar)

4.1 Policy making

- When creating OS policies, it is important to keep in mind their practicability for those who have to implement them.
- Top-down pressure may be counterproductive: Policies have the potential to move OS forward, especially if they are designed in a bottom-up and top-down process at the same time. Especially important is the support of and the acceptance by researchers.
- Researchers have to be provided with the means and infrastructure to comply with policies.
- Communicating the existence and content of policies is very important. Likewise, communication concerning the effects of compliance with policies, e.g. highlighting best practice examples, is vital.

¹See also the consultation on the FAIRsFAIR website: <https://fairsfair.eu/fairsfair-data-object-assessment-metrics-request-comments>, last accessed 13 February 2021.

- Countries differ regarding the funding structure of research and career opportunities for researchers. Consequently, different types of organisations (e.g. universities or funding bodies) bear a different weight when it comes to the impact of their policies on OS.
- Open Science can be considered as a paradigm change of how science and research should be conducted. Therefore, the implementation of this change requires time and patience. We are still at the beginning of this process and therefore should not expect researchers to change the way they work from one day to another due to a policy.
 - Encouraging open access publications and policies thereon has been a goal since the 1990s. This change was more simply achieved since it ‘only’ required a change in the business model of publishers. On the contrary, opening data requires an entirely new concept in academia.

4.2 Communication

- Effective communication is a key factor for successful change. Since there are many stakeholders involved in opening science, they need to work together closely to use synergies and knowledge. In addition, the benefits of OS need to be communicated clearly.
- Communication is especially important to connect actors who stir, design and implement policies. Different stakeholder groups (e.g. politicians, university managers) have similar discussions, but do not collaborate enough.
- Similar to how researchers need time to adapt to the concept of OS, drafting policies on this matter should not be rushed. Instead, improved communication between policy makers allows for exchanging experiences and for aligning policies.

4.3 Alignment

- The harmonisation of policies throughout institutions and countries is key to realising the European Open Science Cloud, connecting researchers and data across borders.
- Policies have the potential to move OS forward, especially if they are well aligned across countries and organisations.
- Researchers value alignment as they e.g. receive funding from different funding agencies. Consequently, aligned policies and regulations are an advantage for researchers.
- Too much pushing for alignment may be counterproductive: there are some partic-

ularities that need to be considered. Conventions also differ across disciplines and need to be respected.

- Policies on OS exist on several levels: institutional policies, regional policies, national policies, and European policies. These ‘layers’ have to be respected when drafting policies as top-down pressure may not be successful in the long run if researchers are not engaged.
- An important aspect of alignment is streamlining our expectations of FAIR data: We need to find a definition for the basic criteria of FAIR data that is commonly agreed upon. Hence, we require minimum criteria as well as optional guidelines for assessing when data can be considered as FAIR.

4.4 Rewards and penalties

Concerning measures to enhance the compliance with RDM policies, the discussion showed a preference for support and rewards over penalties.

- The primary goal of many organisations is to support researchers, not to penalize non-compliance. If researchers do not comply with policies, the first step should be to support them better and discuss their needs.
- Infrastructures, resources and knowledge how to comply with policies are essential and must be provided. Else, researchers cannot comply – no matter how grave the penalties may be.
- Rewards are also a key factor to enhance compliance. If there are rewards for opening research, researchers will more likely comply.
- Communication and framing are important: Calling policies ‘guidelines’ is more attractive to researchers than calling them ‘regulations’. Framing policies as a ‘guide-line to get your reward’ is probably the best way to motivate researchers to comply with policies.
- However, if there are no consequences for researchers who repeatedly violate regulations and do not even try to comply, this may undermine the policies.

5 Conclusion and recommendations

In the discussion, the experts drew the following conclusions on what is needed to enhance the effectiveness of and compliance with policies.

First, good communication throughout all implementation levels is needed to make the content, the use and the benefits of OS policies clear. Also, communication between the different stakeholders is important, to exchange experiences, ensure an adequate level of

alignment of policies throughout institutions and countries and to learn from best practice examples.

A second key factor is to put effort in motivating and supporting researchers to implement OS policies, e.g. by providing the necessary resources, clear guidelines, and rewards.

Last but not least, making science and data open and FAIR is a paradigm change in academia that will take time. This process will not be achieved (by policies) from one day to the next, but requires patience, a lot of communication, learning, training and support.

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